

Smart Metal Organic Frameworks for Sensing Volatile Organic Compounds "SmartMOFs"

Drug@MOFs

Khaled Hassanein, Barbara Ventura

ISOF - Istituto per la Sintesi Organica e la Fotoreattività.
Via P. Gobetti, 101 - 40129 Bologna

What are Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs)

MOFs are a class of porous materials combining metal units – including metal ions organic ligands (linkers) that connect the metal centers into two or three-dimensional periodic structures.

The potentiality of MOFs arises from the existence of unlimited possible combination of metals and ligands and the possibility of fine tuning the structural/function by changing the starting building blocks or through post-synthetic modification and/or Reticular synthesis

The diverse synthetic approaches enrich the field of MOFs with wide range of rational structure with tunable properties, pore shape/size.

Preparation of MOFs

- The properties of MOFs depend on the composition (Both, the ligands and the metals can produce MOFs with Electronic, Optical, Magnetic properties).
- In addition, the nature of the pores (hydrophilic/hydrophobic) and shape/size of the pore make MOFs potential materials for several applications such as, gas separation and storage, sensing of different molecular species.

MOFs as Chemical sensor

MOFs can host different molecules such as gases, ions, or liquids and as a result of the host-guest interaction between MOF molecules and the guest (VOCs), MOFs might produce change in their Physical properties (Sensing applications)

Innovation in MOFs industry

Commercial MOFs by BASF company

MOFs organize the storage of natural gas molecules so that more fuel is stored in the same tank.

SmartMOFs

The main objective of *SmartMOFs* is to design multifunctional (combination of optical and electrical signals) and dynamic Stimuli-Responsive Metal Organic Frameworks (SR-MOFs) with enhanced selectivity and sensitivity towards harmful volatile organic compounds (VOCs), to be integrated into sensory devices.

Create MOFs with free functional groups, which will decorate the MOFs internal surface for establishing specific interactions with the guests (VOCs).

The construction of a sensory device requires a physical interface between the MOF and the device support, which implies fabricating the MOF as a thin film on a surface. *We will use the state of arte in thin-film growth techniques*

Acknowledgement

H2020-MSCA-IF-2016-751175 project "SmartMOFs" is gratefully acknowledged

References

1. Bobbitt, N. S. et al. Metal-organic frameworks for the removal of toxic industrial chemicals and chemical warfare agents. *Chemical Society Reviews* 46, 3357-3385, (2017).
2. Stassen, I. et al. Correction: An updated roadmap for the integration of metal-organic frameworks with electronic devices and chemical sensors. *Chemical Society Reviews* 46, (2017).
3. Stavits, V., Talin, A. A. & Allendorf, M. D. MOF-based electronic and opto-electronic devices. *Chemical Society Reviews* 43, 5994-6010, (2014).
4. Rubio-Martinez, M. et al. New synthetic routes towards MOF production at scale. *Chemical Society Reviews* 46, 3453-3480, (2017).
5. Stock, N. & Biswas, S. Synthesis of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs): Routes to Various MOF Topologies, Morphologies, and Composites. *Chemical Reviews* 112, 933-969, (2011).
6. Kreno, L. E. et al. Metal-Organic Framework Materials as Chemical Sensors. *Chemical Reviews* 112, 1105-1125, (2012).